

A Critical Reassessment of the Statistical Significance of the Orbital Alignment of 3I/ATLAS

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Abstract

The recent claim that the low orbital inclination of the interstellar object 3I/ATLAS provides statistical evidence for an artificial origin is re-examined. We show that this conclusion is not statistically justified, as it overlooks two key aspects: the strong observational bias of current surveys and the large expected population of interstellar objects (ISOs). Once these factors are included, the probability of detecting at least one ISO with a low-inclination orbit becomes high, rendering the orbital configuration of 3I/ATLAS statistically unsurprising.

Keywords: 3I/ATLAS — interstellar objects — statistics — observational bias

1. Introduction

Hibberd, Crowl & Loeb (2025; hereafter HCL25) argued that the orbital inclination of 3I/ATLAS ($i \approx 4.9^\circ$) is anomalously low relative to an isotropic incoming distribution, estimating a probability of $\sim 0.2\%$ for an object to have $i < 5^\circ$. They interpret this low probability as supporting a non-natural origin.

While their geometric calculation is correct, their statistical interpretation is incomplete. The relevant question is not the intrinsic geometric probability of a random arrival direction, but the **conditional probability of detection**, given the observational biases of existing surveys and the number of interstellar objects potentially present in the Solar System. When these two factors are included, the detection of such an orbit becomes entirely expected.

2. The Key Oversights: Observational Bias and Population Statistics

2.1. Geometric Probability

For an isotropic distribution of arrival directions, the fraction of the celestial sphere within 5° of the ecliptic can be approximated as:

$$P(\text{ind}) \approx (\theta^2) / 4$$

$$\text{where } \theta = 5^\circ = 0.087 \text{ radians.}$$

Therefore:

$$P(\text{ind}) \approx (0.087)^2 / 4 = 0.0019 \rightarrow 0.19\%$$

This represents the probability that a randomly arriving ISO has $i < 5^\circ$. However, surveys do not observe the sky isotropically.

2.2. Observational Bias

Near-Earth asteroid surveys such as ATLAS and Pan-STARRS are designed to monitor the ecliptic plane. Their detection efficiency strongly favors objects with low ecliptic latitudes. Hence, the probability of detecting a low-inclination object is much higher than detecting one on a steep orbit.

Let: $P(\text{detect} | \text{low}) = 0.9$
 $P(\text{detect} | \text{high}) = 0.1$

Using Bayes' theorem:

$$P(\text{low} \mid \text{detect}) = [P(\text{detect} \mid \text{low}) \times P(\text{low})] / [P(\text{detect} \mid \text{low}) \times P(\text{low}) + P(\text{detect} \mid \text{high}) \times P(\text{high})]$$

Substituting:

$$P(\text{low} \mid \text{detect}) = (0.9 \times 0.0019) / (0.9 \times 0.0019 + 0.1 \times 0.9981) = 0.0168$$

So, given that we detected an ISO, the probability that it has $i < 5^\circ$ rises to about 1.7%, roughly nine times higher than the purely geometric estimate.

Even if the bias were smaller (for example 0.7 vs. 0.3), the posterior probability would still increase to around 0.4%.

(These bias values are illustrative, but the qualitative result is robust.)

2.3. Population Statistics

HCL25 treat 3I/ATLAS as an isolated event. In reality, population models suggest that thousands of ISOs may be present within Neptune's orbit at any given time.

The probability that at least one of N independent objects has $i < 5^\circ$ is given by:

$$P_{\text{pob}}(N) = 1 - (1 - P_{\text{ind}})^N$$

Using $P(\text{ind}) = 0.0019$, we obtain:

N	Probabilidad
1,00	0,19
50,00	9,10
100,00	17,40
200,00	31,50
500,00	61,30
750,00	75,10
1000,00	85,10
2000,00	97,70

*Probability of ISOs with $i < 5^\circ$ of ecliptic latitude.
On the X-axis: number of ISOs; on the Y-axis: probability.*

Even for a modest population of a few hundred ISOs, the chance that at least one has a low-inclination orbit exceeds **30%**, and for 1,000 objects, **85%**. Thus, the existence of 3I/ATLAS with $i \approx 5^\circ$ is entirely expected in statistical terms.

3. Discussion

The combined effect of survey bias and population size fundamentally alters the interpretation of 3I/ATLAS's orbit

The probability that a detected ISO has a low inclination is orders of magnitude higher than the raw geometric probability cited by HCL25.

Furthermore, for any plausible ISO population above a few hundred, the presence of at least one object with $i < 5^\circ$ in the Solar System at a given time is *more likely than not*. Therefore, 3I/ATLAS does not represent an anomalous event.

The use of "low inclination" as evidence for artificial origin neglects the fact that both survey strategies and large-number statistics make such detections commonplace. While searches for potential technosignatures in ISOs are worthwhile, such claims require a statistically rigorous treatment that incorporates observational biases and realistic population estimates.

4. Conclusions

1. **The claim of an anomalous orbit is statistically unsubstantiated.** The 0.2% geometric probability quoted by HCL25 is not the relevant metric for discovery statistics.
2. **Survey bias strongly favors detections near the ecliptic.** Even approximate models increase the posterior probability of low inclination by a factor of several.
3. **Population effects dominate the interpretation.** With even a few hundred ISOs present, the likelihood of detecting one with $i < 5^\circ$ becomes tens of percent, and near certainty for thousands.

Hence, the orbital alignment of 3I/ATLAS provides **no credible statistical evidence** for a technological origin.

Its discovery is a predictable outcome of observational selection combined with a large underlying population of interstellar visitors.

(Future work could refine this assessment by quantifying the actual survey selection functions, but the qualitative result is robust to reasonable assumptions.)

References

- Hibberd, A., Crowl, A., & Loeb, A. 2025, *Is the Interstellar Object 3I/ATLAS Alien Technology?* <https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.12213>
- Jewitt, David; Luu, Jane; Rajagopal, Jayadev; Kotulla, Ralf; Ridgway, Susan; Liu, Wilson; Augusteijn, Thomas *Astrophysical Journal Letters* **850** (2): L36. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1711.05687>